

Growth, Challenges, and Issues Related To Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (Msmes) In Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:

Micro small and medium enterprises play a crucial role in the socio-economic development of any country, especially for developing countries like India. It helps in creating employment opportunities, exports, gross industrial value of output contribution to G.D.P., boosting manufacturing, service, and infrastructure sectors of the economy. It retains the strategic important role in Uttar Pradesh MSMEs are complementary to large industries as ancillary units and these sectors contribute significantly to the inclusive industrial development of the country. The study is focusing on the growth, challenges and issues related to MSMEs in Uttar Prade

Keywords: - MSMEs employment growth, challenges, infrastructure, inclusive development.

Introduction: -

Uttar Pradesh is a state in the northern part of India covering an area of 2,40,928 km² equal to 7.3% of the total area of India and is the fourth largest Indian state by area. The state is divided into 18 divisions and 75 districts with Lucknow as the capital of Uttar Pradesh. The state has the population of 2,41,066,874 standing at first position population wise. The economy of Uttar Pradesh is the third largest state economy in India with Rs. 17.05 Lakh crore (US \$220 billion) in G.D.P. and a per capita GSDP of Rs. 65,431 (US \$860) Agriculture is the main occupation of people in Uttar Pradesh and plays a vital role in economic development of the state. The MSMEs generate 6,50,000 employment opportunities across the state. Uttar Pradesh has been emerging as the fastest developing state by enhancing its scope in various fields with the help of government initiatives. It has several locally specialized business clusters such as sports items in Meerut, brassware in Moradabad, Perfumes in Kannauj, leather in Kanpur, shoes in

Agra, embroidered and skills sarees in Varanasi, carpet in Bhadohi, chikan work in Lucknow etc. The MSME also plays an important role in the development of the economy with their effective, efficient, flexible, and innovative entrepreneurial spirit (Dey, 2014). As per the Government of India (2000), the small-scale undertakings are those which are engaged in manufacturing, processing or preservation of goods and in which the investment in fixed assets, whether held on ownership terms or on lease or by hire purchase does not exceed Rs. 1crore. After the enactment of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises Development Act 2006, Small Scale Industries have been classified as Micro, Small and Medium enterprises. The Government of India has recently notified a new criteria for classifying the enterprises and has also introduced Udyam Registration instead of all the earlier registration procedures. An enterprise is classified as a Micro Small and Medium Enterprises based on the following composite criteria: -

Table-1 Classification of MSMEs

Type of Enterprises	Investment in Plant & Machinery not exceeding	Turnover not exceeding
Micro	Rs. 1crore	Rs. 5crore
Small	Rs. 10crore	Rs. 50crore
Medium	Rs. 50crore	Rs. 250crore

• **Excluding export Turnover**

Source: - Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises

2-Objective of the Study: -

The objective of the study is to briefly highlight on growth potentials of micro, small and medium enterprises, identify the opportunities available for development of this sector, challenges and constraints controlled by these enterprises and to offer suggestions to overcome the same.

3-Methodology:

The study involves a critical analysis of functioning of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Uttar Pradesh and intends to identify the potentialities for

growth, opportunities, major issues and challenges experienced by these enterprises.

4-Sources of Data: -

The data are collected mostly from secondary sources by way of access to various Government policies/programmes including published Annual Reports, Journals, Books and available official websites, press releases etc. MSME sectors contribution in country's growth and development consistent and remarkable over the preceding decades Statistics show that the number of each enterprise have increased form about 1.1crore in 2001-02 to 4.1crore units in 2009-10 and again to

4.48 crore enterprises in 2014-15. The number of MSMEs in India increased by a CAGR of 18.5% from 2019 to 2020. The MSMEs are widening their domain across sectors of the economy producing a diverse range of products and services to meet demand of domestic as well as global markets. The MSMEs in India are playing a crucial role by providing large employment opportunities at comparatively lower capital cost than large industries as well as through industrialization of rural & backward areas inter alia, reducing regional imbalances, ensuring equitable distribution of national income & wealth.

As per the Annual Report (2018-19) of the Ministry of MSMEs, Government of India, the share of MSMEs in the country's G.D.P. is around 28.9% MSMEs also contribute 48.1% of the total exports from India,

6.11% of G.D.P. from the manufacturing sector and 24.63% of G.D.P. from service sector. The share of MSME GVA in G.D.P. at current prices (2011-12) for 2018-19 and 2019-20 stood at 30.5% and 30% respectively (as per the ministry of statistic & programme implementation). Further, according to the Directorate General of Commercial intelligence and statistics, the share of exports of specified MSME related products to all India exports during 2019-20 and 2020-21 was 49.8% and 49.5% respectively Under the Prime Minister Employment Generation programme (PMEGP), the estimated no of employment generated (No. of persons) in Micro Enterprises during the year 2020-21 and 2021-22 as on (01-07-2021) was 5.95 lakh and 1.19lakh respectively. Below is the number of MSMEs currently registered in Uttar Pradesh.

Table-2 Estimate No. of Enterprises

Type	No. of Units in Uttar Pradesh (in lakh)
Micro	89.64
Small	0.36
Medium	0.00
Total MSME	89.99

Source – MSMEs Annual Report 2020-21

Table-2 shows that the estimated number of enterprises in Uttar Pradesh under micro units category is 89.64lakh, whereas small enterprises are 0.36 lakh totalling to total MSMEs in Uttar Pradesh to 89.99 lakh.

5-Growth Potential in Uttar Prade -

Uttar Pradesh is rich in natural resources with abundant minerals, forest, flora, and fauna. It has well developed scope for food processing and agro based industries. It has a strong source base for mineral resources like marble, bauxite non plastic fire clay, uranium, limestone dolomite glass sand. Uttar Pradesh is landlocked but has good connectivity in terms of roads, railways and air to other parts of the country. Government in partnership with private

sectors have inked a pact for various infrastructure development programmes U.P. is having a strong base for its key traditional industries comprising handicrafts, leather goods, carpet, textile, sugar, cotton yarn, jute, vegetable oil, glassware, bangles and cement etc. Uttar Pradesh has 21 notified, 12 operational SEZs and 24 formally approved SEZs. Merchandise exports from Uttar Pradesh reached US \$13.80 Billion in 2017-18 and US \$ 16.29 Billion in April 2018-March 2019. The exports from Uttar Pradesh Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises have clocked almost 6% growth to touch Rs. 890 billion during 2017-18 exports from U.P. have grown in the MSMEs sector under the following categories.

**Table-3
 Categories of Leading MSMEs sector exports from Uttar Pradesh**

MSMEs	Growth (%)
Leather & Leather goods	11.3%
Carpets and Mats	11.4%
Glass and Glassware	14%
Readymade Garments	13.3%
Meat & Edible Meat	11.3%
Plastics and Articles	6.6%

Source – Compiled from MSMEs Annual Report

The large disparity between the eastern and western U.P. is another challenge, But due to the expressway connecting Purvanchal districts with Delhi, two airports including an international one at Kushinagar and promotion of local products and handicraft have opened up the region to investment and job opportunities which will boost the economy.

The strong point of the state is that it has a rich labor pool. It has a large base of skilled

semiskilled and unskilled labor making it an ideal destination for MSMEs sector.

6- Major challenges faced by MSMEs in Uttar Pradesh: -

MSMEs contribution in the economy of states like Uttar Pradesh is noteworthy. However, MSMEs face many challenges in its way that are described below:

Financial Issues: -

In the Indian economy access to finance has always been an issue for smaller firms and business. The industries and MSMEs sectors of Uttar Pradesh also face the same hindrance of finance. They face difficulties in accessing cheaper credit from formal Banks.

Regulatory Issues: -

Various regulatory issues are also creating problems for MSMEs sectors. Regulatory issues like tax compliance changes in labor laws as a result it has become very difficult for MSMEs to comply with these regulations and register for tax compliance and leading them to shutting up.

Infrastructure: -

The infrastructure facilities are important for MSME sector development which are not very developed in Uttar Pradesh where focus should be drawn

Low Productivity: -

MSMEs are not necessarily very productive. It may become productive. It may become productive only when it becomes cost efficient and is capable of creating high volume at very low cost.

Technical Changes: -

There has been a dearth of technical changes overtime, and most industries have undergone some form of change in order to remain competitive. As a result, Indian MSMEs have had to deal with some very important changes which have affected their growth potential.

Other Challenges: -

The MSMEs in Uttar Pradesh suffer from various other issues as mentioned below-

- Unduly delayed payments by large industry players.
- Low managerial capability.
- Limited capital and knowledge.
- Ineffective marketing strategies.
- Non identification of new markets.
- Hurdles in growth, expansion, modernization and innovations.
- Lack of adequate warehousing facilities.
- Lack of skill and trained workforce.
- Ruthless competition

Issues Related to MSMEs in Uttar Pradesh: -

The state has made some headway in building an environment that supports investment, but much more has to be done in order to make this a reality. Stakeholders have raised many problems during meetings related to 'Evaluation of competitiveness among North India state's,' which is being carried out by CUTs international.

Problems with the single window solution concerns have been voiced by the sector over the ineffectiveness of U.P. Government's single window system approvals. The time frames set out in the act and government order are not being followed. Adding to the complexity, other windows

are hidden beneath the main one, making it difficult to complete tasks.

- Udyog Bandha's dysfunctional high-powered committee has been established to address the challenges encountered by enterprises and to provide recommendations on ways to simplify the rules-Industry association from all throughout the state are also permanent members along with principal secretaries from several departments relating to industry. There's been a lack of cooperation among members of the committee over the last several years, though.
- Institutional memory is lacking because of frequent bureaucratic turnover, the system's institutional memory is at risk.
- Power is expensive, high cross subsidies in the state have led to complaints from industry over the state's high industrial tariffs. This adds to the total cost of doing business for the industry.
- The availability of financing for businesses, the state finance corporation (SFC) and the bank are unable to meet the financing needs of the micro, small and medium enterprises MSMEs.
- Due to lack of a well-functioning land bank as in the case of most other North Indian states the state lacks a functional land bank mechanism to help with land allocation for companies. There is a lot of land in the state of Uttar Pradesh that has been purchased by the government but has yet to be used for industrial development.
- EoDB changes haven't been sufficiently communicated to industry. The situation is exacerbated for small and medium sized businesses (SMEs) who are often left in the dark about existing norms and regulation and must thus rely on intermediaries to do routine tasks.
- When it comes to political sensitivities the political climate in the state of Uttar Pradesh is quite delicate as a result any new initiatives will face a significant degree of political opposition. This complicates the process of drafting and implementing policies.

Suggestions: -

According to the study and analysis of research topics the following suggestions are recommended for the growth and development of MSMEs in India.

1. Easy Credit Availability: -

Banking system of Uttar Pradesh must provide sufficient and easy credit to MSMEs to fulfill their requirements related to establishment and operational activities at a reasonable rate with less complicated documents.

2. Conducting Training & Development Awareness Programs: -

The Ministry of MSMEs and Uttar Pradesh Government must make proper arrangements for conducting Training & Development Programmes to impart knowledge related to technical know-how. There are currently running programs which are not so effective and sufficient may be due to lack of awareness or knowledge about their likely benefits.

3. **Relaxation in Labor Laws & Red Tape: -**

There should be relaxation in complex labor laws to avoid inconvenience in compliance. Red tape must be avoided so that MSMEs can perform smoothly and efficiently.

4. **Easy Availability of Technologies: -**

The number of appropriate technologies for the MSME sector have developed in various sectors. The technologies must be made easily available to MSMEs so that they can perform efficiently and uninterruptedly.

5. **Proper Research & Development: -**

There should be proper research and development undertaken in respect of innovative methods of production and service rendering. The innovative products will provide cost efficiency and more customer satisfaction and the MSMEs of Uttar Pradesh will be able to cope up with the situation.

Conclusion: -

MSMEs sectors have immense potential in Uttar Pradesh in employment generation or export contribution; it is proving itself as a growth booster of the Indian economy. The U.P. government is putting efforts to boost the growth of MSMEs. After analyzing the performance of MSMEs in Uttar Pradesh it can be concluded that MSMEs a blooming sector of Uttar Pradesh and have a huge potential in longer from development prospects.

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